

ENERGYHOLE AND COVERAGE HOLE AVOIDANCE IN UNDERWATER WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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Abstract:

Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks (UWSNs) play an important role as these deploy underwater sensors (nodes) to monitor the parameters of interest. The sensed information is then sent to off-shore sink(s) where it is interpreted to take proper actions. Underwater communication is carried via acoustic modems and communication above the surface of water is carried via radio modems. Due to the limited battery capacity of sensor nodes, minimization of energy consumption is a potential research area in underwater wireless sensor networks (UWSNs). Here it addresses the energy hole creation issue in depth based routing techniques, and devises a technique to overcome the deficiencies in existing techniques. Besides addressing the energy hole issue, the proposition of a coverage hole repair technique is also a part. In areas of the dense deployment, sensing ranges of nodes redundantly overlap. The proposed technique takes a benefit of redundant overlapping and repairs a coverage hole during network operation. The simulation results show that network lifetime and throughput of the network have improved.

Key Words: Underwater Wireless Sensor Network, Energy Hole, Routing, Energy Efficiency & Coverage Hole

1. Introduction:

Most of our planet is covered by water. As more research is being done on underwater systems, data collection and environment monitoring become apparently major players. This raises the need for an effective way to collect data and monitor the environment. Underwater wireless sensor networking offers an unmatched option. The characteristics of the underwater environment present researchers with many challenges especially effective communication and sensor localization techniques. In terrestrial wireless sensor networks, the nodes use radio frequency (RF) to build up the communication. In addition, recent research has shown manifold interest in underwater environment due to expanded application horizon including: detection of underwater oilfield reservoirs, exploitation of undersea minerals, providence of tsunami warnings, monitor-ship of undersea deployed expensive equipment's, mine reconnaissance, [2], etc. In underwater environments, due to water absorption, radio does not work well. Compared to radio waves, sound has superior propagation characteristics in water, making it the preferred technology for underwater communications. In fact, radio waves propagate at long distances through conductive seawater only at extra low frequencies (30—300 Hz), which require large antennae and high transmission power [2]. Optical waves do not suffer from such high attenuation but are affected by scattering. Moreover, transmission of optical signals requires high precision in pointing theatrics narrow laser beams. Thus, most of underwater networks use acoustic signals to communicate to each other [3][4]. Authors in [7] point out the highly dynamic network topology of UWSNs which requires frequent exchange of messages (high overhead) among the sensor nodes for proper network functioning. Being small in size, the underwater sensors operate on tiny batteries (limited energy resource) to perform collaborative tasks [8]. In most of the underwater routing techniques, data packets travel from bottom to top in multi hop fashion. Sink nodes normally float on water surface. Therefore, nodes near sink are engaged in heavy relaying of data which leads to the creation of energy hole and coverage hole. Another consequence of energy hole is network partitioning which ultimately leads to collapse of the entire network [9]. Coverage hole is the phenomenon which arises due to energy hole or regular death of a node. The area where coverage hole is created becomes unsensed. In random deployment of nodes, it is also caused by uneven distribution of nodes in the network field. Because random deployment of nodes causes few areas of network to be more populated while leaving other areas less populated such that less populated network areas are more prone to coverage holes. In this research work, which is extended form of our previous work in [13], we propose a coverage hole repair technique for UWSNs. Initially, we analyse depth based routing which enables us to identify the spots where most of the energy is consumed. Then, we propose a technique to balance the energy consumption of nodes. Our proposed technique not only identifies redundant coverage areas but also fills the hole area by moving nodes from redundant coverage areas to the hole area. Subject to evaluation of our proposed work, we conduct simulations and results justify its effectiveness in terms of the selected performance metrics. Thus, towards energy efficiency in UWSNs, our contribution will benefice the research community

2. Related Work and Motivation:

In existing system, improvement of energy efficiency is a potential research area in UWSNs because limited

energy source of nodes is one of the major constraints in the long term operation of UWSNs. Therefore, intelligent and efficient utilization of energy is needed not only to prolong network lifetime but also to avoid creation of energy holes and coverage holes. The energy efficient routing plays an important role in other techniques of energy conservation. In most of the underwater routing techniques, data packets travel from bottom to top in multi hop fashion. Sink nodes normally float on water surface. Therefore, nodes near sink are engaged in heavy relaying of data which leads to the creation of energy hole and coverage hole. Another consequence of energy hole is network partitioning which ultimately leads to collapse of the entire network. Coverage hole is the phenomenon which arises due to energy hole or regular death of a node. The area where coverage hole is created becomes un-sensed. In random deployment of nodes, it is also caused by uneven distribution of nodes in the network field. Because random deployment of nodes causes few areas of network to be more populated while leaving other areas less populated such that less populated network areas are more prone to coverage holes. Li et al investigated the problem of uneven energy consumption in a large class of many to one sensor networks. In a many-to-one sensor network, all sensor nodes generate constant bit rate (CBR) data and send them to a single sink via multihop transmissions. This type of sensor network has many potential applications such as environmental monitoring and data gathering. Based on the observation that sensor nodes sitting around the sink need to relay more traffic compared to other nodes in outer sub-regions, for analysis verifies that nodes in inner rings suffer much faster energy consumption rates (ECR) and thus have much shorter expected lifetimes. They term this phenomenon of uneven energy consumption rates as the “energy hole” problem, which may result in severe consequences such as early dysfunction of the entire network. They proposed analytical modeling for this problem, which can help understand the relevance of different factors on energy consumption rates. Using this model, they studied the effectiveness of several existing approaches towards mitigating the “energy hole” problem, including deployment assistance, traffic compression and aggregation. In this paper, we are motivated from EEDBR [15] and HORA [11], and focus at their improvement in the following aspects. To minimize the packet loss, high energy consumption and high throughput and to maximize the network lifetime and avoiding the multi-path fading, technique called Depth Based Routing (EEDBR) is introduced. A residual energy (RE) factor is calculated. Due to the introduction of this factor, nodes with higher RE gain the priority of forwarding data. This technique balances the overall energy consumption in the network up to some extent. However, EEDBR achieves this goal at the cost of frequent knowledge sharing among nodes. Because RE of the nodes is continuously changing during network operation and if it is not timely updated then nodes may choose infeasible forwarders. In EEDBR, frequent execution of Knowledge Acquisition Phase (KAP) consumes surplus energy. However, updating knowledge of nodes, on the basis of which nodes select next forwarder, is necessary. However, KAP execution frequency setting leads to a trade-off between energy consumption and information update. The main aim is to minimize the energy consumption cost while keeping the nodes updated. In EEDBR, nodes use static transmission power level as per maximum transmission power level. As a consequence, nodes waste energy in case of near transmissions. Thus, an adaptive power control should be aimed. In random deployment of nodes, uniform distribution of node density in the network field cannot be guaranteed. In energy constrained networks, node death is a regular phenomenon due to which coverage holes are created. A hole repair mechanism is used to find the overlapping of sensing discs and then filled the coverage hole by minimizing overlapping of sensing discs. Since radio waves are not practical in underwater environment, the acoustic waves have been replaced. For location information, we use Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) as location finder [13], and use Mote Track location identification scheme [14].

3. Short: Spherical Hole Repair Technique:

A Spherical Hole Repair Technique (SHORT) takes into account dead/alive nodes for repairing coverage holes which are created due to energy holes. Let the nodes are randomly deployed in a three dimensional underwater network area. In order to restrict the movement of nodes due to ocean currents these are anchored with wires and a floating mechanism. Variable length of wire with each node represents depth of a node. The longer the length of wire is, the shorter the depth of the node will be and vice versa. Sensor nodes (nodes) are assumed to sense underwater environmental data and transmit the sensed data to the sink nodes (sinks). Assume that all nodes are capable of acting as forwarders. These nodes are equipped with multi-power acoustic modems. Thus, the nodes adjust their transmit power levels according to the location of intended next hop node. Sinks float on the surface of water and communicate with nodes and off-shore monitoring station via acoustic and radio modems, respectively. Assume that packet received at sink is delivered to monitoring station. The network model under discussion is assumed to be homogeneous in terms of initial energy and communication capabilities of all nodes. The diagram for deployment of sensor nodes and sink nodes in UWSN is shown in the figure 1

Figure 1: Diagram for deployment of sensor nodes and sink nodes in UWSN

The four modules of the proposed system are classified as follows:

- ✓ Node Deployment for UWSN
- ✓ Knowledge Sharing Phase (KSP)
- ✓ Network Operation Phase (NOP)
- ✓ Hole Repair Phase (HRP)

Node Deployment for UWSN: Assume there are N Sensor nodes (nodes) and M sink nodes (sinks) that are distributed in X×X square field and consider all the nodes are stationary. Each node equipped with same initial energy value. The sink node is placed on top of the water and each sensor node communicates with neighbour sink nodes. Communication takes place by the greedy approach. By this approach nodes in this path are the only eligible ones to forward the data packet. Sensor nodes (nodes) are assumed to sense underwater environmental data and transmit the sensed data to the sink nodes (sinks). SONAR concept is used to calculate signal to noise ratio (SNR) and source intensity (S_i).

$$S_i = SL - TL$$

$$SNR = SL - TL - NL$$

Where, SL=Source level and TL=Transmission loss

To calculate spreading loss: Attenuation or path loss that occurs in an underwater acoustic channel over a distance (l) for a signal of frequency (f) is given by,

$$A(l, f) = l^k a(f)^l$$

Where k is the spreading factor, and a(f) is the absorption coefficient expressed in dB, the acoustic path loss is given by,

$$10\log A(l, f) = k*10\log l + l*10\log a(f)$$

Knowledge Sharing Phase (KSP): Sensor nodes share their depth, residual energy information among their neighbours. First list contains node IDs and nodes use information of this list for data forwarding and the receiver nodes with matching IDs accept the data packet. Dead nodes are discarded from this list time to time during the updates. Second list contains the node IDs which are within sensing radius(r) of the node and used to find out the status of the node as CT, HCT, and NCT. The knowledge acquisition process is as follows: Each sensor node broadcasts a Hello packet to its one hop neighbours. The Hello packet contains the depth and the residual energy of the broadcasting node. Upon receiving the Hello packet, the neighbouring nodes store the depth and the residual energy information of those sensor nodes having smaller depth. The neighbouring nodes only store the information about the sensor nodes having smaller depths since it is obvious that the data packets are transmitted towards the sink nodes residing on the water surface. Hence, storing the depth and residual energy information of all the neighbouring nodes is not required, which lessens the burden of storing a large number of data.

Network Operation Phase (NOP): When network starts operation, all nodes record neighbour information regarding overlapping of sensing ranges. Whenever, a node dies, neighbouring nodes move to fill the hole. The distributed algorithm decides which node has the highest priority to move first. This ensures no new coverage hole creation as a node moves to fill the existing coverage hole. Completion of KSP triggers the start of NOP. In this phase, data packet is forwarded from source node to sink node that may or may not involve intermediate nodes. If the next hop node is sink, packet is reached destination. If the next hop node is not sink, then the following three operations are performed.

Data Aggregation: The forwarding nodes transmit aggregated received data from other nodes and its own data to the next node.

Holding Time Calculation: Each node transmits the received packet after waiting for the calculated *Ht* to expire.

$$Ht = (1 - (\text{current energy}/\text{initial energy})) * \text{max holding time} + p$$

Where max holding time is a system parameter (i.e., the maximum holding time a node can hold a packet), and p is the priority value.

Data Forwarding: On receiving data packet(s), the receiver node embeds IDs of all its neighbouring nodes in the data packet, performs data aggregation and calculates holding time. After elapsing (Ht or MaxHt), the receiver node transmits the data packet.

Hole Repair Phase (HRP): In order to maximize the lifetime of UWSN, it is necessary to maintain connectivity between nodes. As in depth based routing techniques, data packet travels from bottom to top, the death of a node in an established path of traffic flow not only creates hindrance in flow but also creates coverage hole (the area becomes unsensed). This work determines that how this hole can be filled by moving neighbouring node. In this phase the node which moves to fill the coverage hole is known as mobile node. A mobile node could be a CT, HCT, or NCT node, however, CT and HCT nodes have highest priority to become mobile node. A node which is going to be mobile must not lose its existing connectivity. Each node considers a candidate node. The node, which mobile node selects to reduce overlapping is known as assistant node. Selection of mobile node helps in finding the amount of distance to move for mobile node. By using distance and direction to move mobile node to fill coverage hole of the network.

Selection of Mobile Nodes:

The node which moves to fill the coverage hole is known as mobile node. Each node is considered as candidate node. Candidate node observes two constraints prior to become a mobile node

- ✓ A node which is going to be mobile must not lose its existing connectivity
- ✓ Mobility of candidate node must not create any coverage hole

All candidate nodes collect the following information about their one-hop surrounding nodes

- α: Cardinality of set of one-hop adjacent nodes ,
 - ✓ Node(s) must be a CT or HCT node
 - ✓ If both a and b are true then α = x, else α = 0

β: Cardinality of set of NCT nodes which are one-hop adjacent with candidate node: If the candidate node is not a surrounding node then β = x, else β = 0

γ: Number of NCT nodes of candidate node provided: If the number of NCT nodes ≥ 1 then γ = 1, else γ = 0

ρ: Number of intersection points within or on the surface of the spherical region induced by the candidate node. To identify the neighbour distribution of a candidate node

$$C_{val} = \begin{cases} \beta - \alpha - \rho; \beta > \gamma \text{ or } \gamma = 0 \\ \gamma - \alpha - \rho \end{cases}$$

Nodes with highest C_{val} is (are) selected as mobile node(s).

Selection of Assistant Node: The mobile node which selects to reduce overlapping is known as assistant node. Selection of assistant node helps in finding the amount of distance to move for mobile node. Mobile node selects node with maximum value of (θ) as its assistant node.

Distance and Direction of Mobile Node to Move:

CASE 1 - Mobile node is a CT or HCT node: It calculates overlapping area with its assistant nodes. In order to avoid creation of new coverage hole due to mobility, mobile node can only move till the overlapping distance.

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 + y^2 + z^2 &= r^2 \\ (x - d)^2 + y^2 + z^2 &= r^2 \end{aligned}$$

By solving the equations (4.7) & (4.8) for x,

$$X = \frac{1}{2}d \tag{4.9}$$

Placing the value of x in equation (4.8) and solving to get,

$$y^2 + z^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{4r^2 - d^2}$$

Figure 2: Overlapping distance of sensing ranges of two nodes

Intersection of two spheres always results in a lens shaped region as shown in figure 2

$$a = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{4r^2 - d^2}$$

Where a is the equation of circle with radius. The height (radius) of this lens is calculated in equation. To calculate the width of this lens and is similar to circle intersection. Consider the right triangle BEC, by using Pythagorean Theorem the d value can be find as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2}{4} &= \frac{a^2}{4} + r^2 \\ d &= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{4a^2 + r^2} \end{aligned}$$

ALGORITHM: FIND COORDINATES OF NEW LOCATION

INITIALIZATIONS

Dist-to-move = d

SP (x_1, y_1, z_1) //Start Point Co-ordinates

PP (x_p, y_p, z_p) = SP //Previous Point Co-ordinates

```

HP (x2, y2, z2) //Hole Point Co-ordinates
LP (x1, y1, z1) = HP //Last Point Co-ordinates
Point Found = FALSE
mid-point = (xm =  $\frac{(x_1+x_2)}{2}$ , ym =  $\frac{(y_1+y_2)}{2}$ , zm =  $\frac{(z_1+z_2)}{2}$ )
new-dist =  $\sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}$ 
END INITIALIZATIONS
while (NOT Point Found)
  if (new-dist == dist-to-move)
  then
    Point Found = TRUE
    RETURN mid-point
  else
    if (new- dist > dist-to-move) then
      LP = mid-point
      mid-point (xm =  $\frac{(x_m+x_p)}{2}$ , ym =  $\frac{(y_m+y_p)}{2}$ , zm =  $\frac{(z_m+z_p)}{2}$ )
    else
      PP = mid-point
      mid-point (xm =  $\frac{(x_m+x_1)}{2}$ , ym =  $\frac{(y_m+y_1)}{2}$ , zm =  $\frac{(z_m+z_1)}{2}$ ) end if
    end if
    new-dist =  $\sqrt{(x_m - x_1)^2 + (y_m - y_1)^2 + (z_m - z_1)^2}$ 
  end while

```

If the co-ordinates of mobile node are H(x1, y1, z1) and the co-ordinates of dead node are H(x2, y2, z2), then the algorithm 1 finds the co-ordinates of new location for mobile node to move.

CASE 2 - Mobile node is a NCT node:

- ✓ If more than one NCT nodes are surrounding nodes, then node with highest O-max value moves first
- ✓ It finds its assistant node and calculates its new location co-ordinates. After completion of its mobility, next NCT surrounding node with second highest value of O-max starts its movement in the similar way. The process continues until all surrounding NCT nodes complete their movement to fill the hole

CASE 3 - Cascading mobility of CT/HCT and NCT nodes:

- ✓ Prior to their movement, the NCT nodes broadcast an invitation message to CT/HCT nodes in their vicinity to move first, thus take the benefit of their overlapping
- ✓ A CT/HCT node when hears an invitation message, it first checks its qualification for movement then the CT/HCT node moves as in CASE 1
- ✓ NCT node then calculates its overlapping distance with neighbouring CT/HCT node and finds co-ordinates of new location using algorithm
- ✓ If NCT node does not find any neighbouring CT/HCT node then first it finds its assistant node and then moves in the direction of hole.

4. Result Analysis:

Short technique is compared with EEDBR where the SHORT saves the energy by using multiple power transmission levels. SHORT makes CT/HCT nodes to sleep which are redundant in the initial phase of the network operation. The initial nodes of SHORT die early, the reason is that initially due to few sleep nodes, less number of nodes participates in the network operation, and therefore forwarding load on few nodes increases. However, it does not affect the network lifetime as sleep nodes replace the dead nodes. The following are the parameters which are taken into account for comparison.

- ✓ Growth in coverage volume by increasing node density
- ✓ Rate of alive nodes
- ✓ Packets reception rate at sink
- ✓ End to end delay

Growth in Coverage Volume by Increasing Node Density:

In Figure 3 shows that coverage volume grows exponentially with increase in node density. As dense node deployment leads to relatively high overlapping volume which means that more volume is covered and the chances of coverage hole are thus minimized as for as initial phases of the network operations are considered

Figure 3: Growth in coverage

Rate of Alive Nodes:

It is evident from the figure 4 that network lifetime of SHORT is 59% more than EEDBR and 145% more than DBR. The possible reasons are: SHORT conserves energy via pick a back technique, SHORT saves energy by using multiple power transmission levels SHORT makes CT/HCT nodes to sleep which are redundant in the initial phase of the network operation. The initial nodes of SHORT die early, the reason is that initially due to few sleep nodes, less number of nodes participates in the network operation, and therefore forwarding load on few nodes increases. However, it does not affect the network lifetime as sleep nodes replace the dead nodes. Nodes in EEDBR actively participate in the network operations that lead to high energy consumption.

Figure 4: Packet delivery ratio

Packets Reception Rate at Sink:

The throughput of SHORT is higher than its competitor protocols. Main reason behind higher throughput is nodes longer lifetime. Sleep nodes take over the responsibility of forwarding data packet as any of the boundary node dies. Therefore, more nodes send data packets for longer period of network lifetime.

Figure 5: Throughput

End to End Delay:

End to end delay of SHORT is higher than the competitor's techniques. The basic reason behind higher end to end delay is considering processing time for removing coverage hole. The hole repair algorithm is distributed. Therefore, all nodes involve in the coverage hole repair process which consumes time and ultimately affects packet delivery time. The cost of end to end delay is paid to achieve the benefits of network connectivity, throughput and energy conservation..

Figure 6: End to delay

5. Conclusion:

The proposed scheme is based on reducing the energy hole and coverage hole and these are the issues that degrade the performance of UWSNs in terms of network lifetime and throughput. The former is created due to unbalanced or extra energy consumption of nodes in the network. The later one may arise due to energy hole, regular death of a node or random deployment of nodes. A technique knowledge sharing phase is introduced to reduce the energy consumption of a sensor. Movement of a node is restricted to overcome the creation of new coverage hole. Finally, validate the improved performance of the work in terms of the selected performance metrics through comparative simulations. In future, the CBC-MAC - cipher block chaining message authentication code technique may be introduced for constructing authentication code from block cipher. The main advantage is that the message is encrypted with some block cipher algorithm in CBC mode to create a chain of blocks such that each block depends on the proper encryption of the previous block. Encrypted block will change in a way that cannot be predicted or counteracted without knowing the key to the block cipher.

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